

Open Data in DESI Countries

Angelo Leogrande¹

The use of open data grew between 2016 and 2021 by an amount equal to 7.64 units or by an amount equal to 218.79%

It is an indicator that considers two elements, namely: to what extent does a country have open data policies and what are the political, social and economic impacts of open data. The variable takes into account the functionality, the availability of data and the use of national open data portals. The historical series analyzed is between 2016 and 2021. The United Kingdom is excluded from the calculation of the constituent variables of the DESI Index.

Ranking of European countries by value of open data. Denmark is in first place with an open data value of 13.67, followed by Spain with a value of 13.49, and France with an amount of 13.47. In the middle of the table are Greece with a value of 12.18 units, followed by Finland with a value of 12.15 units and Slovenia with a value of 12.01 units. Portugal closes the ranking with an amount of 6.8 units, followed by Malta with a value of 6.71 units and Hungary with a value of 4.82 units.

Ranking of countries by value of the absolute change in the value of open data between 2016 and 2021. Denmark ranks first by value of the absolute change in open data between 2016 and 2021 with a value of 9.56, followed by from Spain with a value of 9.44 units, and France with a value of 9.42 units. In the middle of the table there are Greece with a value of 8.52 units, followed by Finland equal to an amount of 8.50 units, and Slovenia equal to a value of 8.40 units. Slovakia closes the ranking with a value of 3.71 units, followed by Hungary with a value of 3.38 units and Portugal with a value of 2.99 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm. A clustering is presented below through the use of the k-Means algorithm optimized through the Silhouette coefficient. The analysis shows the presence of two different clusters, namely:

- Cluster 1: Malta, Portugal, Slovakia, Hungary, Belgium, Luxembourg;
- Cluster 2: Romania, Czech Republic, Bulgaria, Latvia, Denmark, Spain, France, Croatia, Ireland, Sweden, Slovenia, Estonia, Poland, Austria, Finland, Greece, Netherlands, Lithuania, Germany, Italy, Cyprus.

From the metric point of view it appears that the value of the median of cluster 2 is equal to an amount of 12.21 while the value of the median of cluster 1 is equal to an amount of 7.22 units. It therefore follows that $C2 = 12.21 > C1 = 7.22$.

Machine Learning and predictions. An analysis is carried out below through the use of a comparison between 10 different machine learning algorithms for predicting the future value of the value of the open data variable. The algorithms are trained with 80% of the available data. A ranking is made based on the algorithms' ability to maximize R-squared and minimize MAE, MSE, RMSE statistical errors. Below is the ordering of the algorithms based on performance, that is:

- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 4;
- SGD with a payoff value of 8;
- AdaBoost with a payoff value of 12;

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- Gradient Boosting with a payoff value of 16;
- Random Forest with a payoff value of 20;
- kNN with a payoff value of 24;
- Tree with a payoff value of 24;
- SVM with a payoff value of 31.
- Constant with a payoff value of 36;
- Neural Network with a payoff value of 40.

Therefore the Linear Regression algorithm is the best predictor for the historical series of the Open Data variable in the analysis of the DESI Index dataset.

Network Analysis with Manhattan Distance. Below is an analysis with the network analysis tool optimized with the distance to Manhattan. Specifically, complex network structures are identified, i.e. structures having more than three nodes and simplified network structures or structures having only two nodes.

There is a complex network structure between Greece, the Netherlands, Lithuania, Finland, namely:

- Greece has a connection with the Netherlands for a value of 0.0078, with Finland for a value of 0.015 units, with Lithuania for a value of 0.023 units;
- The Netherlands has a connection with Greece for a value of 0.0078 units, with Finland for a value of 0.023 units and with Lithuania for a value of 0.015 units;
- Lithuania has a connection with the Netherlands for a value of 0.015 units, with Greece for a value of 0.023 units, with Finland for a value of 0.039;
- Finland has a connection with the Netherlands for a value of 0.023, with Lithuania for a value of 0.039, with Greece for a value of 0.015.

There is a connection between Austria, Poland and Estonia. Particularly:

- Austria has a connection with Poland for a value of 0.031 units;
- Poland has a connection with Austria for a value of 0.031 units and with Estonia for an amount of 0.074 units;
- Estonia has a connection equal to a value of 0.074 with Poland.

There is a connection between Cyprus, Italy and Germany, namely:

- Cyprus has a connection with Italy for a value of 0.027;
- Italy has a connection with Cyprus for a value of 0.027 and with Germany for a value of 0.085 units;
- Germany has a connection with Italy for a value of 0.085.

There is a two-way relationship between the following countries, i.e. .:

- Sweden and Slovenia have a connection worth 0.039;
- France and Spain have a connection worth 0.012 units.

Conclusions. The use of open data is still very low in DESI countries. In the most advanced country in terms of Open Data, namely Denmark, the variable reached the value of 13.67 units. In many countries the variable is stable below the value of 10, including Germany where the value is 8.76 and Italy with 8.68 units. If the possibility of using open data is scarce, the ability to do business with open data is obviously even rarer. There are still too few companies able to do business with open data through the use of machine learning, artificial intelligence and big data. There are certainly

opportunities for improving the public administration, which, however, are not adequately seized by public bodies. It follows that both the private sector and the public sector are far behind in the use of open data and in doing so increase the distance between the potential economy and the real economy.

Declarations

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L'utilizzo degli Open Data nei Paesi DESI								
Countries	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	Var Ass	Var Per
<i>Austria</i>	★ 3,86	★ 5,13	★ 6,82	★ 8,42	★ 10,39	★ 12,82	★ 8,97	★ 232,46
<i>Belgium</i>	★ 2,68	★ 3,57	★ 4,74	★ 5,85	★ 7,22	★ 8,92	★ 6,24	★ 232,46
<i>Bulgaria</i>	★ 3,34	★ 4,44	★ 5,90	★ 7,28	★ 8,99	★ 11,10	★ 7,76	★ 232,46
<i>Croatia</i>	★ 3,54	★ 4,70	★ 6,25	★ 7,72	★ 9,53	★ 11,76	★ 8,22	★ 232,46
<i>Cyprus</i>	★ 3,72	★ 4,95	★ 6,58	★ 8,12	★ 10,02	★ 12,37	★ 8,65	★ 232,46
<i>Czechia</i>	★ 3,10	★ 4,12	★ 5,48	★ 6,76	★ 8,35	★ 10,31	★ 7,21	★ 232,46
<i>Denmark</i>	★ 4,11	★ 5,47	★ 7,27	★ 8,97	★ 11,08	★ 13,68	★ 9,56	★ 232,46
<i>Estonia</i>	★ 3,90	★ 5,19	★ 6,90	★ 8,51	★ 10,51	★ 12,97	★ 9,07	★ 232,46
<i>Finland</i>	★ 3,66	★ 4,86	★ 6,46	★ 7,98	★ 9,85	★ 12,16	★ 8,50	★ 232,46
<i>France</i>	★ 4,05	★ 5,39	★ 7,17	★ 8,84	★ 10,92	★ 13,48	★ 9,42	★ 232,46
<i>Germany</i>	★ 3,77	★ 5,01	★ 6,66	★ 8,22	★ 10,15	★ 12,53	★ 8,76	★ 232,46
<i>Greece</i>	★ 3,66	★ 4,87	★ 6,48	★ 7,99	★ 9,87	★ 12,18	★ 8,52	★ 232,46
<i>Hungary</i>	★ 1,45	★ 1,93	★ 2,57	★ 3,17	★ 3,91	★ 4,83	★ 3,38	★ 232,46
<i>Ireland</i>	★ 3,97	★ 5,28	★ 7,02	★ 8,66	★ 10,70	★ 13,20	★ 9,23	★ 232,46
<i>Italy</i>	★ 3,73	★ 4,96	★ 6,60	★ 8,15	★ 10,05	★ 12,41	★ 8,68	★ 232,46
<i>Latvia</i>	★ 3,45	★ 4,59	★ 6,10	★ 7,53	★ 9,29	★ 11,47	★ 8,02	★ 232,46
<i>Lithuania</i>	★ 3,67	★ 4,88	★ 6,49	★ 8,02	★ 9,89	★ 12,21	★ 8,54	★ 232,46
<i>Luxembourg</i>	★ 2,78	★ 3,70	★ 4,92	★ 6,07	★ 7,49	★ 9,25	★ 6,47	★ 232,46
<i>Malta</i>	★ 2,02	★ 2,69	★ 3,57	★ 4,41	★ 5,44	★ 6,72	★ 4,70	★ 232,46
<i>Netherlands</i>	★ 3,67	★ 4,88	★ 6,48	★ 8,00	★ 9,88	★ 12,19	★ 8,52	★ 232,46
<i>Poland</i>	★ 3,87	★ 5,15	★ 6,84	★ 8,44	★ 10,42	★ 12,87	★ 9,00	★ 232,46
<i>Portugal</i>	★ 3,87	★ 2,74	★ 3,65	★ 4,50	★ 5,56	★ 6,86	★ 2,99	★ 77,30
<i>Romania</i>	★ 3,87	★ 3,95	★ 5,25	★ 6,49	★ 8,01	★ 9,88	★ 6,01	★ 155,38
<i>Slovakia</i>	★ 3,87	★ 3,03	★ 4,03	★ 4,97	★ 6,14	★ 7,58	★ 3,71	★ 95,76
<i>Slovenia</i>	★ 3,61	★ 4,80	★ 6,39	★ 7,88	★ 9,73	★ 12,01	★ 8,40	★ 232,46
<i>Spain</i>	★ 4,06	★ 5,40	★ 7,17	★ 8,86	★ 10,93	★ 13,49	★ 9,44	★ 232,46
<i>Sweden</i>	★ 3,61	★ 4,80	★ 6,38	★ 7,88	★ 9,73	★ 12,01	★ 8,39	★ 232,46
<i>Media</i>	★ 3,52	★ 4,46	★ 5,93	★ 7,32	★ 9,04	★ 11,16	★ 7,64	★ 218,79

